

Online Post Mail in Nepal: A Theoretical Study

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Abstract: Online post mail introduced by Department of Postal Service Nepal have has a promising applications, if used properly. In this paper, we have studied the problems and solutions to it.

Introduction:

Online post mail, as introduced in Nepal requires physical post box number, and post box, for sending and receiving letters. As told by officials in General Post Office, Charkhal Dillibazaar, online post mail has introduced only in Kathmandu district. That raises a problem, that any people wanting to have online post box number, has to get physical post box number from Kathmandu. That effects peoples, as any people wanting to have online post mail has to get, another post box number from Kathmandu Valley. That results in having two post box number by same individual, as per two different geographical places.

Two or more than two post box number for an individual:

Having two post box number for an individual would address place of residence, based on temporary and residence, but would still result in requirement of two postal address for any individual.

Online Postal Mail:

Use of online mail by decentralizing can provide us with solution to the requirement of two post box number for any person. Let us consider an example with author and his post box number. Author's post box number is 1(Post Office Box number), issued from District Post Office, Jhapa. When online post mail is taken, by the same post box number, then by means of web pages, or app, author can send and receive letters, and parcels, based on his current place of residence, by providing geographical location, and nearest location of Post Office, or address of receiptants. That means, place of receipt can be made flexible, irrespective of place of issue of post box number, as Post Box number are placed on permanent

basis for any location. That would solve problems for personal post box number, as individual can send and receive from nearest post office, across entire Nepal. For organizational, and institutional post box number, as they have physical infrastructure, place of organizational, and institutional address can be talked. That means for personal physical post box number, introduction of app, to include online post box number would be more efficient for sending and receiving any items from postal service. It concludes, each Area Post Office too must need to have working practises for online and offline post mail services, where as personal, and organizational/institutional post box numbers must be seperately classified, so that both of post box numbers can be widely used.

For Parcels, offline services are necessary, whereas for letters, online services too can be introduced in the same way as of manuscript tracking and it's response, found in journals [1] Making plafom of submission manager in app, would make it much more flexible, for inter-office works between any two offices, or even between any two individual. For that, introduction and use of two different post box number: individual, and organizational/institutional is necessary. Post-Man, and Vehicles delivering the posts and parcels can be tracked by use of their mobile devices, where our letter or parcel has arrived in physical location, and for that, safety too has to be studied based on the materials that we do send and receive.

Recent Trends:

Nagarik App, introduced by Government of Nepal (Nagarik App; Google Playstore), has features for submission of complaints by means of online platform. Similiar type of app can be introduced for tracking of materials send through postal services, amd inter-official work purposes to send and receive letters and parcels. App would then allow us to find out about our letters, receiving and registration of letter done by administration, then about work to be done as per letters.

Comments by Author:

Author had send application letters [2], to postal services in Nepali language, and this work too, is a solution for application letter send to author regarding, residence and migration based on place of residence, by means of online post mail. This work thus is a translation, as well as explanation of application letter send to postal office administration of Nepal.

Application of Postal Sciences:

Postal sciences can be studied, to know about internet, as post mail is similiar to that of email that we widely use by means of internet, for sending and receiving letters at certain email address. We can study especially about distance, and time, along with addresses between sender and receiptant as per various protocols of internet.

References:

[1] Arjun Dahal. (2021). Development of Postal Office Theory. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5256117>

[2] Arjun Dahal. (2021). Application Letters, and Other Documents. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4933945>

[3] Arjun Dahal. (2021). On Standarization of Addresses. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4904541>